

Advance Social Science Archive Journal

Available Online: <https://assajournal.com>

Vol.3 No.1, January-March, 2025. Page No. 2221-2233

Print ISSN: [3006-2497](#) Online ISSN: [3006-2500](#)

Platform & Workflow by: [Open Journal Systems](#)

THE TEACHERS' UNDERSTANDING REGARDING THE IMPACT OF PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT ON EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION AT PUBLIC SECTORS SCHOOLS IN PAKISTAN: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY

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ABSTRACT

One of the key factors in ensuring that children continue to learn and develop successfully is parents' engagement in their education as parents are the ones who know their children the best. The settings that relate to the teacher, school, or institution should be prepared and meet the needs of each child. In accordance with teachers' point of view the parents at public sector school don't show interest or involve in their children's academics in Sindh Pakistan. Therefore, the objective of the study was to identify and analyze the teachers' perception of parent involvement, frequent involvement of parents and effects of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

The present study is suitable for the improvement of learning and developing early childhood education, leading to improved results for children. The current study is a significant quantitative study that gathered data through a questionnaire. In order to acquire a broad understanding of the impact of parents' engagement in their childhood education a large sample of data was collected.

The results suggested, in accordance with teachers' understanding that parents do not frequently involve in their children's early childhood education. This low parental involvement causes the poor academic performance of their children in early childhood education at public sectors schools in Sindh Pakistan.

Keywords: *Teachers' perception of Parental Involvement, Impact of Parental Involvement, Public Sectors Schools, Sindh Pakistan.*

1.1 Introduction

An essential instrument for the advancement of civilization is education. (Rafiq et al, 2013). The advancement of society relies on people's knowledge and education and the development of education is concerned with children's academic success (Rafiq et al, 2013). The society is connected with families. The life of the students associates with their parents and they see their parents as the role model and first teacher (Wasim et al, 2008). Parents mention mothers & fathers who are accountable for the children's education and also for the advancement of society. Kaiser & Hancock (2003) mentioned that early development and

academic achievement are related to family background, parents serve as their children's initial instructors. Furthermore, Rafiq et al (2013) claim that a child stays with his parents during the early stages of life so parents are responsible for the education and early development of the child. The financial responsibility of the family is related to the father and on the other hand mother stays at home and takes care of the children (Talib, 2009). Somehow, in developing countries like Pakistan, parents are unable to focus on their children's academic performance (Rasool & Zhang, 2020). It is because due to the lack of interest and also the rising inflation. Parents in Pakistan force their children to work rather than get an education (Ahmed et al, 2014). As a result, the parents do not involve in their children's education.

It has been observed that public-sector school learners failed to get good results and were also unable to compete with private-sector students. A possible reason could be poor parental involvement in learners' academic progress (Gordon & Cui, 2014). It has also been noticed that the parents of public sector school learners do not focus on their children's academic development. The parents just sent their children and raise their hands from all academic responsibilities of their children. Therefore the children's academic results decline and they do not perform well. In Pakistan, Ali et al (2022) claimed that students declined in their academic results when their parents didn't focus or take an interest in their children's academic performance. The parents usually rely on the school teachers or management and do not emphasize children's education. In Pakistan, the parents who send their children are usually at work and also force their family to work, to fulfill the monthly financial expense.

As a teacher, it has been an alarming situation. The students failed to do homework and also did not perform in the class. Their parents do not come to the parent-teacher meeting. The learners were quite satisfied with their home because their parents didn't ask or discuss anything about schoolwork or academic progress. Pakistan is a developing country and the only way to get the country develop is the education. The poor parental involvement is directing Pakistan toward its downfall.

Parents are considered important people for the advancement of children's education (Phan, 2004). The parent's involvement should not emphasis on school or teacher learning but parents must focus on the learning through activities. Because the learning activities attract students and it is also the best source of learning. According to Jeynes (2007) parental engagement in the growth of school education has significant benefits. Parental participation is essential for academic progress. Moreover, parental involvement is interrelated with the grade of the students. Likewise, superior parental involvement directs the learners towards better academic performance. Many researchers have discovered that the student's homework and classwork performance gets improved when the parents get involved. Furthermore, the student's academic performance declined when parents showed negative interest (Mphale & Mhlauli, 2014).

Teachers must comprehend learners and how they live, work, and play since they are the experts who guide the educational process. Additionally, parents must comprehend the teacher's point of view. The study is significant because it illustrates how parents and teachers can work together and create durable relationships for the benefit of the children. Making parents aware of the need of participating in their children's educational journey is important.

The purpose of the study is to demonstrate the perception of teacher regarding the concept of parental involvement, frequent involvement of parents and impact of parental participation affects children's academic performance. Understanding the teachers' point of view on why parental participation in schools has decreased is crucial. According to the study's findings, children become more disciplined and tend to earn higher marks when their parents are actively involved in their academic education (Epstein, 2018). The morale of teachers may be raised through parental engagement, which can also foster better parent-teacher interactions. The present study investigates the idea of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan from the perspectives of teachers. To make the educational system more autonomous and to take into account increased accountability by schools to society. Therefore, the present study will be the guidelines for educators and also the parents. This will help implication for the children's academic progress.

1.2 Aim

The present study aims to investigate the teacher's understanding of parental involvement at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan. Moreover, it will also discover the effects of parental involvement at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

1.3 Research Objectives

- To explore the teachers' perception regarding the concept of parental involvement on early childhood education at public sector schools in Pakistan?
- To find the frequent parental involvement in early childhood education at public sectors schools in Sindh Pakistan?
- To discover the effect of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

1.4 Research Questions

1. What is the teachers' perception regarding the concept of parental involvement on early childhood education at public sector schools in Pakistan?
2. How frequently do the parents involve in early childhood education at public sectors schools in Sindh Pakistan?
3. How far does parental involvement affect in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

2.1 Literature Review

The focus of the literature review is on teachers' perceptions of parental participation. The viewpoints of the instructors are important because they make it simpler to create plans for fostering closer ties between educators and parents, which will raise pupils' academic performance. The teacher-parent relationships significantly address a number of issues, including the lack of parental involvement in schools, poor communication between the school and parents, and the failure to offer programs that involve both parents and teachers. As a result this lacks the children poor academic progress. Teachers are the initial point of contact for parents and, according to Epstein (2018), teacher support for engaged parental engagement improves kids' academic progress. The relationship between the school and home determines whether a parental participation program is successful or unsuccessful (Gonzalez et al., 2013). For the benefit of the pupils, research by Epstein (2018) and McCaleb (2013) has shown that instructors must be at the forefront of building a positive relationship

between the school and family. As a result, when teachers and parents work together to create partnerships, they have the chance to build relationships with parents who are not actively participating in their child's education (McCaleb, 2013). However, Teachers are essential in assisting children in the classroom and including parents in their children's education. (Bonk & King, 2012; Darling-Hammond, 2012).

A child's first teachers are their parents. Through regular contact, dialogues, and activities, they teach kids to language, communication, and fundamental ideas. Parents who engage in educational play, reading, and discovery help create the groundwork for lifelong learning. By interacting with teachers, attending parent-teacher conferences, and helping in school events, parents actively engage in their child's early childhood education. Parents give educators and administrators insightful input on their children's experiences in early childhood education settings (Llamas & Tuazon, 2016). They share their findings, issues, and recommendations, which influence the early childhood education programs' curricula, instructional strategies, and general level of quality. By fostering a conducive learning environment at home, parents help their children learn outside of school. In addition to providing educational tools and engaging in activities that support their child's cognitive, social, and emotional development, parents often reinforce principles that are taught in school. According to Budhrani et al (2021), parents may assist their children as they advance in their education by assisting them with their homework, assignments, and study techniques. They establish a routine, provide direction, and emphasize the need for accountability and time management. Furthermore, parents build an environment where inquiries are accepted and investigation is encouraged to nurture curiosity and critical thinking in their children (Lilly, 2014). Children are challenged to think critically and analyze their surroundings through the discussions. Parents can improve the efficacy of early childhood education by encouraging learning at home. Instilling a passion for learning in children is mostly the responsibility of their parents (Wolf, 2020). By encouraging discovery, stimulating curiosity, and recognizing their child's accomplishments, parents help their children develop a good attitude toward school. Parents contribute to the general growth of early childhood education by encouraging a love of learning in their children. Early childhood education has been greatly influenced by parents (Ginsberg, 2007). Parents contribute to the development and improvement of early childhood education programs and ensure the best outcomes for their child and other children through active involvement, advocacy, feedback, Parents work to enhance early childhood education programs and guarantee their children receive the greatest results. When parents collaborate with teachers to encourage learning at home, they are fostering a love of learning and adding to the cultural and linguistic richness of their children.

The important influence that parents play in their children's development has been the subject of several studies. W. H. Jeynes (2005) investigated the relationship in urban primary schools between parental involvement and academic achievement. In urban primary schools, the connection between parental participation and academic success is examined in this meta-analysis. It highlights the significance of parental participation in urban educational settings by demonstrating a favorable relationship between parental involvement and student accomplishment. Dearing, Kreider, Simpkins, and Weiss (2006) explored Low-income children's parental involvement in education and literacy as well as long-term relationships between and within families. This longitudinal research explores the connection between

low-income children's reading outcomes and family participation in the classroom. It proves that family involvement, particularly parental encouragement and support. It has a favorable long-term impact on children's reading development. Furthermore, the effect of family literacy interventions on children's acquisition of reading from kindergarten to grade 3 was investigated by Sénéchal, M., & Young, L. (2008). This meta-analysis investigates how family literacy programs affect kids' reading development from kindergarten to grade 3. It emphasizes the benefits of parental engagement in literacy activities on kids' reading abilities, such as joint book reading and interactive literacy experiences. Additionally, Powell, D. R., Son, S. H., File, N., & San Juan, R. R. (2010) examined parental socialization of emotion expression: Gender differences and relations to child adjustment. This study explored teachers point of view about the concept of parental involvement, frequent participation of parents and the effects of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Approach\Methods\ Tools

The quantitative approach directs the research approach and focuses on gathering and analyzing numerical data to address research questions or test hypotheses (Apuke, 2017). The present study used the descriptive survey method to find the outcomes. It includes using statistical methods for data analysis and inference. A disciplined and methodical manner to analyze data, anticipate the future and test ideas is provided by quantitative methods. The quantitative approach collects data that can be measured and statistically analyzed; it frequently entails the use of surveys, experiments, or other organized data-gathering procedures (Antwi & Hamza, 2015). By using a large sample size and objective, generalizable findings, quantitative methodology aims to enable researchers to conclude a wider population. The quantitative approach helps in getting an overall picture of the phenomenon. This approach not only helps in exploring the teachers' perception regarding the concept of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools but is also useful in discovering the effects of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

3.2 Population & Sampling

The term "population" describes the total set of people or things that a researcher is interested in researching (Etikan et al, 2016). The goal of the research is to extract the findings from the larger group of individuals. (Ishak & AbuBakar, 2016). Sampling is the process of selecting a selected portion of a population to participate in a study. (Mujere, 2016). Since studying the entire population is either impractical or impossible. Therefore the teachers working in Sindh Pakistan are population and all about n=300 teachers were selected as the sampling for the present study. Initially the data analyzed through the research questionnaire. Finally the results were carried out for the concluding outcomes for the present study.

3.3 Research tool

1. Research Questionnaire	To explore the teachers' understanding regarding the concept of parental involvement and also discuss the effects of parental involvement on early childhood education in public sector schools at Sindh Pakistan.	15 questions 300 participants
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Research Questionnaire is considered as a suitable tool for data collection to gain the overall understanding of the research questions. Moreover the participants were asked about the concept parental involvement, frequent parental interference in early childhood education and the effect of parental involvement in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

4 Results & Discussions

4.1 Data Analysis & Discussions

The survey was completed and it was also calculated through the response category of frequencies. Furthermore, the percentage was also measured for each research questions on the Likert scale. For understanding in detail regarding the agenda of parental involvement specific questions was adapted to fulfill the need of current objectives in Pakistani context. The questions were selected to direct the teacher's perspective about the role parental involvement in development of education at public sectors schools in Sindh Pakistan. Below section will try to get the overall insight of research question no.1.

SECTION 1: What is the teachers' perception regarding the concept of parental involvement on early childhood education at public sector schools in Pakistan?

Question 1. Helping in children's homework is parental involvement.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	2	0.6%
Strongly Disagree	21	7%
Disagree	34	11.3%
Agree	98	32.6%
Strongly Agree	145	48.3%

The majority of the teachers indicated that helping children in their homework is parental involvement. More than 80% of teacher showed their strong agreement on above statement. On the other hand, 18.3% of teacher believed that helping students in homework in not parental involvement. Consequently, majority teachers claimed, interfering in homework is parental involvement.

Question 2 Attend parents-teacher meeting is parental involvement

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	07	2.3%
Strongly Disagree	13	4.3%
Disagree	28	9.3%
Agree	119	39.6%
Strongly Agree	133	44.3%

The findings from the above table indicate that 83% of teachers were strongly agreed with the afore-mentioned statement. In contrast, 13% displayed disagreement. According to teachers' understanding that attending parent-teacher meeting is parental involvement.

Question 3. Parents communicate with the school management is parental involvement

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	01	0.3%
Strongly Disagree	04	1.3%
Disagree	19	6.3%
Agree	109	36.3%
Strongly Agree	167	55.6%

The majority of the teachers said that parents 'communication with school management is parental involvement. More than 91% of the teachers expressed strong agreement with the aforementioned remark. However, 7.6% of teachers showed disagreement and believed that the communication with school management about their children is not parental involvement. Therefore, connect with school management about their children is considered parental engagement, according to the majority of instructors.

Question 4. Parents communicate with teacher is parental involvement

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	06	2%
Strongly Disagree	17	5.6%
Disagree	31	10.3%
Agree	102	34%
Strongly Agree	144	48%

Although approximately more than 48% of teachers presented the strong disagreement regarding the concern of parents in their children educational development. On the other hand, 16% teachers displayed positive about the concern of parents. To conclude, parents do not participate and they also do not have any worry about their children education in public sector.

Question 5. Parents volunteer or teach in their children in passing exams is parental involvement

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	02	0.6%
Strongly Disagree	4	1.3%
Disagree	26	8.6%
Agree	115	38.6%
Strongly Agree	153	51%

Above table showed that 89% of teachers strongly agree with the statement.is directed that parents volunteer or teach their child in passing exams is parental involvement. On the other side, 9% showed disagreement with above statement. Hence it has been believed by the teachers that helping or teaching the child for passing or getting good score is parental involvement.

To conclude, section 1 directs the teachers' understanding the concept of parental involvement. It has been found that, helping children to complete homework, communicating with teachers and school management about the child's progress and volunteering or teaching students for passing exams is parental involvement at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

SECTION 2: How frequently do the parents involve in early childhood education at public sectors schools in Sindh Pakistan?

Question 1. Parents frequently help in children's homework.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	09	3%
Strongly Disagree	141	47%
Disagree	127	42.3%
Agree	21	7%
Strongly Agree	2	0.6%

A majority of teachers (89.3%) presented strong disagreement about the statement. Additionally, 7.6% of teachers also showed agreement. Thus, the table directs that parents do not frequently help their children in doing homework, according to teacher's point of view.

Question 2. Parents frequently communicate with the school management.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	12	4%
Strongly Disagree	152	50.6%
Disagree	122	40.6%
Agree	13	4.3%
Strongly Agree	01	0.3%

Hence, mainstream quantity of teacher displayed disagreement on afore-statement. More than 90.6% of teachers directed that parents do not communicate with school management for the betterment of their child's education. The lack of communication between parents and school management directs the poor involvement from parents in early childhood educational development.

Question 3. Parents frequently attend parents-teachers meeting.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	7	2.3%
Strongly Disagree	09	3%
Disagree	14	4.6%
Agree	105	35%
Strongly Agree	165	55%

As a result, the majority of teachers strongly agreed with the previous assertion. More than 90% of teachers gave the instruction that parents do not attend parent-teacher meeting. The possible reason is the parents' lack of participation. This is why students don't show their attentiveness in class.

Question 4. Parents frequently communicate with teacher.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	2	0.6%
Strongly Disagree	135	45%
Disagree	121	40.3%
Agree	32	10.6%
Strongly Agree	10	3.33%

To conclude, the majority of educators refuted the aforementioned claim as a consequence. More than 85% of educators told that parents do not communicate with teacher about their children progress. Since their parents are not seriously concerned with their child's education. This absence of parental involvement may be the cause decline in learners' educational health.

Question 5. Parents frequently volunteer or motivate their children to improve class performance.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	2	0.6%
Strongly Disagree	158	52.6%
Disagree	101	33.6%
Agree	24	08%
Strongly Agree	15	05%

Consequently, the majority of teachers disapproved the aforementioned statement. More than 84% of teachers urged, parents do not motivate their child to improve class performance. It is because the parents don't take their children's education very seriously. The deterioration in students' educational performance might be caused by a lack of parental involvement. This causes students to pay less attention in class performance.

To conclude, the parents do not frequently involve in their children's early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan. The lack of parental involvement has a strong impact over children academic performance. In public sector organization, the early childhood students are unable to perform well in their academic because their parents show disinterest in their children educational development

SECTION: 3 , How far does parental involvement affect in early childhood education at public sector schools in Sindh Pakistan.

Question 1. Those learners, whose parents do not show involvement, always complete their homework on time

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	05	1.6%
Strongly Disagree	121	40.3%
Disagree	135	45%
Agree	35	11.6%
Strongly Agree	04	1.3%

As a result, the vast majority of teachers disagreed with aforementioned claim. More than 86% of teachers indicated, the learners, whose parents do not show involvement, did not always complete their homework on time. Therefore, majority of teachers disagree with

statement that parental involvement in public sectors schools is low and it is affecting the learners' early childhood education.

Question 2. Those children, whose parents do not show involvement, always display good score in reading.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	09	3%
Strongly Disagree	111	37%
Disagree	95	31.6%
Agree	65	21.6%
Strongly Agree	20	6.66%

The overwhelming majority of teachers rejected the aforementioned assertion. More than 67% of instructors reported that students whose parents don't participate in their education don't usually perform well in reading. Contrarily, 27% of participants agreed with the assertion.

Question 3. Those children, whose parents do not show involvement, always display attentiveness in their class.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	12	4%
Strongly Disagree	109	36.3%
Disagree	86	28.6%
Agree	69	23%
Strongly Agree	25	8.3%

The vast majority of teachers disagreed with the aforementioned claim. More than 64% of teachers said that children whose parents don't support their education typically show disinterest or display non-serious behavior in class. On the opposite hand, 31% of participants agreed with the statement.

Question 4. Those children, whose parents do not show involvement, always score good results in exams.

<u>Value Label:</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Don't Know	2	0.6%
Strongly Disagree	129	43%
Disagree	102	34%
Agree	51	17%
Strongly Agree	16	5.3

Over 76% of teachers disagreed with the assertion. Those children whose parents don't support their education often exhibit poor score in exams or behave non-seriously in class, while 22% of participants agreed with it.

To sum up, parents in Sindh, Pakistan, rarely participate in decisions that significantly influence their children's early childhood education. The academic success of children is impacted considerably by parental participation. Early childhood learners in public sector organizations struggle academically since their parents don't care about their children's educational advancement.

4.2 Research Questionnaire Findings 1

The survey results showed that, in teachers' opinions, helping with homework, communication between parents & teachers, and volunteering their child in passing exams is parental involvement (See Section: 1). Additionally, frequent parental participation in early childhood education is now insufficient in public sector primary schools at Sindh Pakistan (See Section: 2). Possibly this is because, for several reasons, including non-serious behavior from parents, weak financial position etc. Secondly, inadequate communication and a lack of understanding between parents and teachers are the two biggest obstacles to efficient parent engagement. Bruin (2018) also supported the idea parents have an important responsibility for the educational development of their children. But they do not get involved in their children at the primary level. The advantages of parental participation and its impact on student's academic progress were also highlighted in the present study.

Thirdly, the harmonious ties between the school and home play a vital part in the development of children's education. Likewise, similar advantages of parental participation in educating children academically were found in Epstein's 2018 study. This study, which is in line with other studies, demonstrates that increasing parental participation has a variety of advantages.

4.3 Research Questionnaire Findings 2

The majority of teachers concur that there is little parental participation has a great impact on the poor academic performance of learners in public schools in Sindh Pakistan. Poor parental involvement leads the poor performance in children's educational development (See Section: 3). It's because parents don't care about their children's grades and academic performance. Consequently, the student's performance is declining. Similarly, Scarpellini et al (2021) found that parents with lesser education levels participate less in extracurricular activities than parents who have greater education degrees. According to the study, the challenge for parents with low educational levels is that they are unable to help their children with their homework or other school-related problems because of their insufficient knowledge. Collaboration, student encouragement, and academic growth are interrelated to parents' involvement. The learners get motivated by the involvement of their parents.

5 Conclusion

The findings from this study are important for comprehending teachers' perspectives on parental involvement in public schools in Pakistan. The teachers' understanding, assisting in homework, communication between parents & teachers, and volunteering their child in passing exams are parental involvement. Furthermore, in public sectors schools has poor parental involvement at Sindh Pakistan. Additionally, poor parental involvement affects the academic performance of children at the early childhood level in Sindh Pakistan. Consequently, the lack of parental involvement directed the learners toward poor academic performance. The

The present investigation also identified ways to boost parental involvement in schooling. The results reveal that parents in Sindh, Pakistan, public schools do not care about their children's prospects, especially in the academic area. Some parents aren't as concerned with their children's futures, in their education, or in preparing them for their futures. Moreover, Brower & Griffin (2011) believed that parental participation is lacking, and this is due to the

school's continued poor communication. It is a high-poverty school, as people spend the day at work.

5.1 Recommendations:

The teachers' suggestions for enabling variables would make it easier to create the right procedures to guarantee the successful completion and integration of school development initiatives into the current educational system. This quantitative exploratory study may be repeated in different contexts where it is unclear what the instructors think about parental engagement. The current study also demonstrated the significant responsibilities that teachers play in children's life when they receive the essential teacher training and development. Teachers will promote increased parental participation in schools if they contact with parents often. As a result, this will affect the academic performance of children in school. A recent investigation indicates that parental involvement is more important to children's academic success. Parental involvement also helps child development in a number of ways. One way that parents may have a beneficial effect on their children's education is by helping them with their homework at home. Children whose parents, assist them with their homework, and provide tutoring using resources provided by teachers often outperform those children who don't have these supports, in terms of academic performance. Additionally, the results of the current study indicate a connection between parental participation and academic performance.

5.2 Practical Implications:

Participants in the present study revealed that instructors are aware of the value of children's academic performance and that they think the school must start initiatives to connect the home to the classroom and educate parents on the significance of parental engagement. The findings suggested that if school-home ties are currently weak, they need to be enhanced via training and communication. The trainings and communications between teachers & parents might have a good impact on students. A leadership team or a working plan that assists parents might be implemented by local schools to enhance parental participation practices. In some schools there are some leadership teams working on creating communication between schools & parents, but if the team could be strengthened by involving more parents, parental participation would increase. According to the study's teachers, this might result in a surge in parental participation, which will have a substantial impact on children's academic progress.

5.3 Recommendation for Future Research

The socioeconomic condition of parents is one of the obstacles to parental engagement in schools, in the teachers' opinion. The case study was conducted at Pakistan's Sindh public schools. As a result, the instructors' opinions on parental engagement were limited to public schools in a single state. Conducting a case study that includes teachers' perspectives on parental participation from various public schools around the whole country is one suggestion.

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